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Research Article

**ENTREPRENEURIAL POTENTIAL AMONG
UNDERGRADUATE PHYSIOTHERAPY STUDENTS OF
LAHORE**¹Adnan Hashim, ²Ifrah Mustafa, ³Sana Shahid, ⁴Hamil Chattha¹DPT student, University Institute of Physical Therapy, University of Lahore.²DPT student, University Institute of Physical Therapy, University of Lahore.³Assistant Professor, University Institute of Physical Therapy, University of Lahore.⁴Former DPT student, University Institute of Physical Therapy, University of Lahore.**Abstract:****Objective:** To determine the entrepreneurial potential among undergraduate physiotherapy students of Lahore.**Study Design:** Cross-sectional survey**Setting:** 10 medical institutes of Lahore.**Participants:** 309 physiotherapy students.**Main outcome measures:** Entrepreneurial potential among physiotherapy students and comparison of entrepreneurial potential between men and women. (measured by scoring of Entrepreneurial Potential Assessment Exam). Data was taken from 10 different medical institutes of Lahore..**Results:** 309 participants from different universities of Lahore participated. Out of which, 29.5% were males and 70.5% were females. Males has more entrepreneurial potential as compared to females. Out of 309 participants, 3.2% has greater entrepreneurial potential, 47.9% students falls intermediate zone, 43% students has weak entrepreneurial potential, 3.9% students lack entrepreneurial potential. Students of mean average 21 years of age have more entrepreneurial potential.**Conclusion:** It is concluded that men have more entrepreneurial potential as compared to females but overall undergraduates of physiotherapy have only 3.2% very high entrepreneurial potential and majority of student fall in intermediate zone of entrepreneurial potential.**Key Words:** Entrepreneurial, Potential, Undergraduate, Physiotherapy, Lahore**Corresponding author:****Adnan Hashim,**

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INTRODUCTION:

The time period “entrepreneur” used to be first posted in 1723 in a French dictionary "Dictionaried Universel de Commerce. (1) Oxford Dictionaries describe “entrepreneur” as “A man or woman who units up a commercial enterprise or businesses, taking on economic dangers in the hope of profit”. Entrepreneurship refers to an individual’s capability to flip thoughts into action. It consists of creativity, innovation and chance taking, as nicely as the capacity to layout and manipulate tasks in order to reap objectives. (2). Entrepreneurship is seen by using economists to be a mixture of innovation and danger taking. When, such exercise thrives, excessive boom fees are done as nicely as possibilities provided to all of society, which include the poor. (3, 4) In these instances of monetary crisis, we are taken by means of the shock through the truth that extra and extra humans are inclined towards placing up their very own ventures in the world of entrepreneurship. This is additionally vital for the economic System and has wonderful influences over person and economic system as well. People decides to come to be an entrepreneur due to many motives like want for monetary independence and security having frustration with their modern place of business and career, sturdy wish for fulfillment and willingness to make investments their sources and having capability to take risk..(5,6). In modern societies, a massive variety of initiatives to promote entrepreneurial moves have been brought in order to reply to one-of-a-kind societal challenges (such as growing older population, regional inequalities, etc.).(7) To this end, schooling is one of the extra frequent approaches thru which entrepreneurial conceivable is promoted and subsequently one of the key areas where we have to inspect the influence of entrepreneurship initiatives at character level.(8, 9) According to Global Entrepreneurship Monitor’s 2010 report, Pakistan lags in start-ups, with much less than 1/2 the price of early-stage entrepreneurial endeavor discovered in different factor-driven economies.(10) Part of the hassle is that most younger human beings coming out of universities pick looking for a job as a substitute of exploring entrepreneurial profession possibilities – one of the key findings of CIPE-P@SHA speak with college students and start-ups. Even younger human beings who select to enter paid employment frequently have bother discovering a job, are badly paid, or wind up in informal or casual jobs, in accordance to the World Bank.(3, 11) Entrepreneurship, especially in relation to small and micro-enterprises, is often considered as a key automobile for employment advent (Folster, 2000), an crucial potential of bettering the innovation dynamic in the local, regional and countrywide economies (Robbins *et al* ,2000) In this way, entrepreneurial initiatives make

contributions to the technique of adaptive remodeling and restructuring of the modern enterprise world, supplying a steady flow of gaining knowledge of experiences and therefore underpinning improvement of a greater sustainable kind (Videira, 2001, prices in Franco,2007). While at a macro-level entrepreneurship is viewed as being accountable for job-creation, innovation and the introduction of wealth, at a greater man or woman level, the improvement of enterprising conduct has been characterized as one of the principal stimuli to the widening of profession options, especially amongst first-time labor market entrants (Reynolds *et al.*, 1994)(12, 13) According to (Awogbenle and Iwuamadi 2010) in growing international locations like Pakistan, early life wants to be inspired toward entrepreneurial things to do as they ought to be a recipe of catastrophe if remained unemployed(14) Traditionally formative years entrepreneurship has now not been influenced in Pakistan nor has it acquired tons interest from extraordinary stakeholders..(15). Young humans need to be analyzed in order to apprehend which elements have an effect on their intentions to start-up a business.(16) Physical therapists are fitness care authorities who maintain, restore, and enhance movement, activity, and fitness enabling humans of all a while to have choicest functioning and exceptional of life, whilst making sure affected person protection and making use of proof to grant environment friendly and fine care (10) . The Bureau of Labor and Statistics USA has predicted a boost in the demand of Physiotherapy services up to 36% by 2022. In an article, published in Time magazine, physical therapists were listed as the sixth most recession-proof job. According to US News and World Report it was included in the list of best jobs in 2012.(17) In Pakistan the quantity of enrollments, in Physiotherapy undergraduate and graduate programs, is on upward thrust ever seeing that the introduction of medical doctor of physiotherapy direction and Masters in specialties. Vision 2020 of APTA stipulates that Physical therapist is an autonomous, first contact practitioner and lets in direct get right of entry to of sufferers to physiotherapy offerings irrespective of referral. However, the area of interest of non-public exercise and sparkling startup stays an undiscovered area amongst most of physiotherapy graduates which is principally due to lack of entrepreneurial training and scarce motivation position fashions for unbiased profitable practice. There is very little or no huge work on this facet of occupation in Pakistan to-date.(18) Therefore this study is unique in sense to shed light on existing entrepreneurial potential among physiotherapy students of Lahore and necessitates implementation of proper educational reforms in present curriculum regarding entrepreneurship.

The rationale of this study was to assess entrepreneurial potential among undergraduate physiotherapy of Lahore.

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Study Design: Cross-sectional survey

Setting: 10 medical institutes of Lahore.

Participants: 309 physiotherapy students.

Main outcome measures: Entrepreneurial potential among physiotherapy students and comparison of entrepreneurial potential between men and women (measured by scoring of Entrepreneurial Potential Assessment Exam). Data was taken from 10 different medical institutes of Lahore.

Sample size: n=309

Sample size was calculated on the basis of given formula:

$$n = \frac{Z_{1-\alpha/5}^2 P(1-P)}{d^2}$$

METHOD:

To collect data empowerment from students will be started by taking compile agreement from the management of the university. A cross sectional survey was conducted at 10 institutes of Lahore including UOL, UCP, superior university, Pak Medical college, UMT, Ghulabdevi, Rashid lateef medical college, university of South Asia, Afro Asian institute of health science, Allama medical college. A total of 309 students who were regular students in physiotherapy in undergraduate program having normal mental and physical health and those are willing to participate were enrolled in this study. Post graduate and PhD students were excluded. An informed consent will be taken from the study participants. All questions in the questionnaire are validated through previous literature. The questionnaire contained 25 questions, which included specific demographic descriptors (such as gender, age, student status). Entrepreneurial potential was directly assessed by asking students to indicate the intensity of their current general interest in creating their own business on graduation, and the extent to which they had taken steps to concretize the intention to establish their own firm with the help of Entrepreneurial Potential Assessment Exam Questionnaire. Questionnaires will be provided and abstracted to the respondents as pamphlet. After the data had been collected, they were analyzed and

interpreted using the statistical software package SPSS.

RESULTS:

A total of 309 students participated in the survey among which 29.5% were males and 70.5% were females.

The mean age of participants was 21. According to Entrepreneurial Potential Assessment Exam the scale of scoring the responses regarding potential for entrepreneurship states that:

- Score: 20-25 shows that You have great entrepreneurial potential.
Entrepreneurship.
- Score: 16-20 shows that you have definite entrepreneurial potential.
Entrepreneurship.
- Score: 11-15 shows that you in an intermediate zone.
Entrepreneurship.
- Score: 06-10 shows that Your entrepreneurial potential seems fairly weak.
Entrepreneurship.
- Score: 06-10 shows that you lack entrepreneurial potential.

The results of the study conducted to determine entrepreneurship potential among students of Physiotherapy in Lahore, Pakistan are summarized, For Q1 4% students replied strongly disagree, 12% disagree, 64% neutral, 14% agree, 89% strongly agree. For Q2 3% students replied strongly disagree, 9% disagree, 63% neutral, 13% agree, 103% strongly agree. For Q3 5% students were strongly disagreed, 36% disagreed, 50% marked neutral, 14% agreed, 78% strongly agreed. For Q4 10% students were strongly disagreed, 49% were disagreed, 70% marked neutral, 12% students were agreed, 60% marked strongly agreed. For Q5 7% students were strongly disagreed, 48% were disagreed, 12% marked neutral, 97% were agreed, 28% were strongly agreed. For Q8 none of the student were strongly disagreed, 4% were disagreed, 23% answered neutral option, 131% were agreed and 15% were strongly agreed. For Q9, 7% students were strongly disagreed, 30% were disagreed, 53% answered neutral option, 13% were agreed and 81% were strongly agreed. For Q10, 6% students disagreed, 40% answered neutral option, 15% agreed and 111% strongly agreed.

Figure 1: Descriptive statistics of Entrepreneurial Potential among males and females.

The above chart indicates the participants from each institution enrolled in this survey. Out of 309, 3.2% has greater entrepreneurial potential (10 males, 0 females), 47.9% students falls intermediate zone (117 females, 31 males), 43% students has weak entrepreneurial potential (85 females, 48 males), 3.9% students lack entrepreneurial potential (10 females, 2 males)Males has more entrepreneurial potential as compared to females.

Figure 2: Descriptive statistics of Entrepreneurial Potential among different age group of students.

Students having age between 20-22 years have more entrepreneurial potential. Mean age of students is 21 who has greater entrepreneurial potential.

Figure 3: Descriptive statistics for Q (When I know I am right, I can convince others?)

Almost 130 students were strongly agreed with this, 115 students were agreed, 40 students replied in neutral, 20 students were disagreed and 5 students were strongly disagreed.

Figure 4: Descriptive statistic for Q (I work better when someone advises or guides me)

Out of 309 participants, majority of students were strongly agreed with this statement while least number of students marked strongly disagreed option.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of Scoring of Entrepreneurial Potential Assessment Exam.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid It would be probably be difficult for you to evolve into business world in present	12	3.9	3.9	3.9
Your entrepreneurial potential seems fairly weak. You would certainly have to reconsider some of your opinions	133	43.0	43.0	46.9
you in an intermediate zone. You are probably capable of going into business, but you would have to put a lot of effort	148	47.9	47.9	94.8
you have definite entrepreneurial potential.however, your success in business could depend on the abilities you show	6	1.9	1.9	96.8
You have great entrepreneurial potential	10	3.2	3.2	100.0
Total	309	100.0	100.0	

Out of 309 participants, 3.2% has greater entrepreneurial potential, 47.9% students falls intermediate zone ,43% students has weak entrepreneurial potential, 3.9% students lack entrepreneurial potential.

DISCUSSION:

In Pakistan, focus about and utilization of physiotherapy offerings is on upward shove ever given that its introduction in 1959 at JPMC Karachi. However, the significance of Physiotherapy offerings has been realized three folds greater in the closing decade in Pakistan specifically after the up-gradation of Physiotherapy educational degree world over. According to VassilisKostoglou et al (2008) gender, degree grade and specialty are the significant factors for intent of entrepreneurship and self-employment. Physiotherapy is the 1/3 biggest strong point with 26.2% self-employment fee in Greece.(19). The effects of this find out about are in consistence with that of VassilisKostoglou. Sarri and Trihopoulou (2005), argued that social elements like dependency and lack of guide are the hurdles for lady entrepreneurs(20) These consequences have been constant with the consequences of the carried out learnthatin whole 60% men possess excessive practicable for entrepreneurship in distinction to

66.75% girl who are least probably to be entrepreneurs in future. Eurobarometer (2007) enunciates that the desire of time and area are quintessential problems to women for exercise as unbiased gurus in the neighborhood (19). Dunn et al. (2000) and Hout et al (2000) located that human beings who owned a household enterprise introduced themselves as the function models to new era and had fantastic influence on their selection to be entrepreneurs(20)Nonetheless, the results of this study contradict with those archived by Babur MN and Arjumand M (2013) regarding the potential of entrepreneurship among physiotherapy students.(21) Alam A et al discovered that only 3.25% students both postgraduate and undergraduate possess very high potential for entrepreneurship, 37.93% have high potential whereas 32.37% have potential but are not likely to be entrepreneurs and 26.47% students lack potential for entrepreneurship. It was also found that junior undergraduate and senior postgraduate students of Physiotherapy exhibited

more potential of entrepreneurship. The current study shows in detail that only 3.2% undergraduate students of physiotherapy have great entrepreneurial potential, 1.9% has definite potential depending on resources, 47.9% falls in intermediate zone, 46.9% seems fairly weak and 3.9% lack entrepreneurial potential. Males have greater entrepreneurial potential than females. The mean age of 21 possess greater entrepreneurial potential.

Strengths: This study has shed light on Entrepreneurial potential among undergraduate students of physiotherapy which helps them to know either they should go for their private setups in future or not Data was collected from large number of medical universities of Lahore. Participants were enrolled without any biasness

Limitations: Data was taken only from institutes of Lahore so the results cannot be generalized for whole world of Physiotherapist where socio political cultures varies from that of Pakistan. Policies regarding autonomy of health care professionals also differ worldwide.

Unanswered questions and future research: Results of this study showed that a very small number of undergraduate students showed very high entrepreneurial potential but we didnot figure out what is the reason behind this. There can be a lot of reasons for this which should be determined in future so that steps should be taken to eradicate that negligence.

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